

ROADMAP

Rethinking of antimicrobial decision-systems in the management of animal production

Research and Innovation action: H2020 – 817626
Call: H2020-SFS-2018-2
Type of action: Research and Innovation Action (RIA)

Literature review of impact assessment applied to changes in antimicrobial use initiatives

Marie-Jeanne Guenin¹, Sophie Molia^{2*}, Merete Studnitz³

¹INRAE, France; ²CIRAD, France; ³ICROFS, Denmark;

* Deliverable leader – Contact: sophie.molia@cirad.fr

DELIVERABLE D6.1

Workpackage N°6

Due date: M18

Revised version on the 04/05/2021

Dissemination level: Public

About the ROADMAP research project

The overall aim of ROADMAP is to **foster transitions towards prudent use of antimicrobials (AMs) in animal production in different contexts to manage antimicrobial resistance (AMR). Prudent antimicrobial use (AMU) will be achieved by enhancing antimicrobial decision-systems along the food and drug supply chains.** ROADMAP will focus on supporting animal health and welfare through prevention and health promotion actions.

AMR is recognized as a significant threat to global public health and food security. Overuse and improper use of AMs in many parts of the world contribute to the emergence and spread of AMR. Although human and animal health require AMs, it has been estimated that two thirds of the future AMU growth worldwide will be in animal production. Improving the management of AMU in farm animals is therefore a critical component of dealing with AMR and optimizing production in the livestock sector. Nevertheless, the variety of contexts of AMU in the livestock sector is a major challenge to managing AMR. **There is no “one-size-fits-all” solution to improve AMU and strategies must be contextually developed** (for instance, strategies used in the Danish pig industry are difficult to adapt and adopt in the French free-range poultry farming). Successful solutions must be combined and tailored to the production systems and the social and economic context in which they operate.

ROADMAP will meet three general objectives, in line with the EU AMR Action plan: i) **Rethink AM decision-systems and animal health management;** ii) **Develop options for encouraging prudent AMU in animal production;** iii) **Engage all actors in the food and drug supply chains in fostering a more prudent use of AMs.**

Project consortium

Part. N°	Participant organisation name (acronym)	Country
1	Institut National de Recherche pour l'Agriculture, l'Alimentation et l'Environnement (INRAE) **	France
2	Association de coordination technique agricole (ACTA) ***	France
3	Centre de coopération internationale en recherche agronomique pour le développement (CIRAD) **	France
4	University of Liverpool (ULIV) *	United Kingdom
5	Cardiff University (CU) *	United Kingdom
6	James Hutton Institute (HUT) **	United Kingdom
7	Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna (UNIBO) *	Italy
8	Aarhus Universitet (AU) *	Denmark
9	Eigen Vermogen van het Instituut voor Landbouw en Visserijonderzoek (EV-ILVO) **	Belgium
10	Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL) **	Switzerland
11	Stichting Wageningen Research (WR) *	Netherlands
12	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU) *	Sweden
13	Southern Agriculture and Horticulture Organization (ZLTO) ***	Netherlands
14	European Forum of Farm Animal Breeders (EFFAB) ****	Netherlands
15	Fundacion Empresa Universidad Gallega (FEUGA) ****	Spain
16	Dierengezondheidszorg Vlaanderen (DGZ) ***	Belgium
17	INRAE Transfert (IT) ****	France

* *Universities/veterinary schools*

** *Research institutes specialized in both fundamental and applied agricultural and veterinary sciences*

*** *Public and private advisory services Organisations*

**** *Knowledge transfer and Innovation organisations*

Table of contents

1 Summary	6
2 Introduction to impact assessment	7
3 Review of impact assessment applied to changes in antimicrobial use initiatives in animal health	8
3.1 Objectives of this review and selection of articles	8
3.2 Summary of findings on initiatives to change AMU	10
3.2.1 Interventions' context	10
3.2.2 Types of approaches and strategies	11
3.2.3 Actors involved, influential and impacted	11
3.2.4 Monitoring and evaluation	12
3.2.5 Outcomes and impacts	13
4 Conclusion	16
5 References	17
6 Appendices	20
Appendix 1: Countries of the 27 reviewed interventions	20
Appendix 2: Production system settings of the interventions	21
Appendix 3: Details about the circumstances of the interventions	21
Appendix 4: Details about the strategies of the interventions	24
Appendix 5: Details about the monitoring of the interventions	28
Appendix 6: Details about the outcomes and impacts of the interventions	31

List of acronyms and abbreviations

AM	Antimicrobials
AMR	Antimicrobial resistance
AMU	Antimicrobial use

1 Summary

The ROADMAP project aims at developing interventions/solutions for encouraging prudent antimicrobial use (AMU) in animal production. **The objective** of activities conducted under **work package 6** is to **improve the construction of these interventions/solutions** by designing them in a strategic and participatory manner and **laying out the mechanisms through which impacts will be generated**.

The aim of this deliverable was to **review the literature on impact assessment applied to changes in AMU initiatives**. Unfortunately, very few proper impact assessment studies have been conducted on the topic of AMU in animal production. Indeed, impacts are long-term effects which are difficult to monitor. The majority of studies assess outcomes (that is changes in behaviours, practices or organisations) in stakeholders directly involved in AMU interventions.

We therefore **enlarged our literature review** to find articles on AMU interventions where **outcomes (and sometimes impacts)** were assessed or expected since the design. Using the **PRISMA method** for literature review, we identified 27 articles describing outcomes and impacts of AMU interventions in various countries and production systems. For each intervention, we analysed the **context**, the **type of approach and strategy** used, the **actors involved**, the **monitoring-evaluation system** set up (including the types of indicators used), and finally the expected and **generated outcomes and the impacts** they contributed to.

Despite the diversity of contexts and types of interventions on AMU reviewed, we were able to identify some **key success factors for acceptance and successful change** (for example farm-specific strategies, based on preliminary diagnostic and proper consideration of farmers' perceptions, with close monitoring and protocols in case of unfavourable outcomes) and **failure factors** that prevent sustainable change and lead actors to revert to previous behaviours once the intervention ends (for example unaddressed underlying health problems or antimicrobials misuse social norms).

We hope this review will be **useful for stakeholders who want to set up interventions for more prudent AMU in animal production**.

2 Introduction to impact assessment

Impact assessment has been increasingly used in the last thirty years to assess interventions in the fields of development, policy-making or research. It consists of **evaluating the positive and negative, intended or unintended, direct or indirect, primary and secondary long-term effects** on final beneficiaries that result from an intervention (Stern et al. 2012). In summary, impacts are what remains after an intervention is completed.

In the case of the ROADMAP project, an **intervention refers to something that has been identified as potentially favouring prudent AMU in animal production**. An intervention can be of different types: providing an awareness-raising course on antimicrobial resistance (AMR) and AMU, setting-up an antimicrobial (AM)-free label, facilitating vaccine use for a disease that otherwise requires antibacterial treatment, introducing a new regulation on AM sales, creating a network of farmers to exchange health management tips, etc.

Impact assessment can be undertaken **ex ante** (before the start of the intervention, in a planning perspective), **ex post** (after the undertaking of the intervention and the observation of impacts), or **in itinere** (while the intervention is being implemented and the impacts are still not evident) (Barret et al. 2018).

In interventions related to agriculture, the challenge for impact assessment is to take into account broad impacts that go beyond economic impacts (for example social, territorial, environmental, political, and health-related impacts) (Joly et al. 2016). This has become more difficult as **agricultural research and innovation systems are increasingly open and complex**, and changing quickly.

Different approaches have been used for impact assessment including:

- **Experimental** approaches: for example randomized control trials, natural experiments or quasi experiments (Banerjee and Duflo 2009) which rely on counterfactual logic (asking the question what would have happened without the intervention)
- **Theory-based**: they rely on identifying causal processes through applications of the theory of change (Alvarez et al. 2014), process tracing, contribution analysis, or impact pathways (Devaux-Spatarakis 2014). Realist evaluations are another theory-based option for identifying causal mechanisms and supporting factors depending on context (Pawson and Tilley 1997)

There is often an assumption that experimental methods are the best method (Stern et al. 2012). However, these designs focused on **attribution** (establishing through quantitative measures a direct link between a cause -often described in medical terms as a “treatment”- and an effect) are very resource-intensive, require very good statistical databases and are difficult to apply in complex contexts.

A systems approach focused on **contribution** attempts to understand the processes and causalities leading to impact and usually consists of a mixture of quantitative and qualitative tools (Morton 2015).

Participatory approaches to impact assessment tend to involve different stakeholders, including beneficiaries, at all stages of the intervention. Stakeholders are involved in both identifying the changes they wish to see, and assessing whether, and how, those changes have been realised.

It should be noted that these different approaches are not mutually exclusive, and that **impact assessment may in some circumstances be carried out through multiple different approaches**.

3 Review of impact assessment applied to changes in antimicrobial use initiatives in animal health

3.1 Objectives of this review and selection of articles

The main objective of this literature review was to provide a summary of findings on impact assessment applied to changes in AMU initiatives in animal health. The steps of the PRISMA method (Moher et al. 2009) were followed for the selection of the articles. We entered the following search equation: TITLE: ("impact assessment*" OR "impact evaluation*") AND TITLE: (antimicrobial* OR "anti-microbial" OR "anti-infective agent" OR antibiotic* OR "anti-biotic") AND TOPIC: (animal* OR livestock* OR herd* OR veterinar* OR poultry OR chicken* OR cow OR calves OR veal* OR beef* OR dairy* OR farm* OR pig) into Scopus, Web of Science, PubMed and CAB Abstracts bibliographic databases. An additional query was performed with Google Scholar. Requests were also sent to all ROADMAP partners to identify publications, grey literature, reports and theses on studies assessing the impact of interventions related to AMU or AMR control in their respective countries.

Unfortunately, these query and request only provided one eligible result (Rademacher et al. 2019) showing that **proper impact assessment methods have hardly been applied to the field of antimicrobial use in animal health.**

We therefore decided to **enlarge this literature review to articles on interventions that aimed to decrease or rationalize AMU in animal health.** We knew we would not find detailed information on all the components of the impact pathway (which encompass inputs, outputs, outcomes and impacts as explained in ROADMAP milestone MS31) but we aimed to identify at least the circumstances and the outcomes generated through these interventions. We also aimed to summarise the **levers and barriers to change**, the different types of approaches to design or implement the intervention, the different **types of strategies**, and the **methods to monitor the outcomes/impacts** of the interventions.

The search equation was modified and became: TITLE: (intervention* OR program* OR planning* OR plan OR polic*) AND TITLE: (antimicrobial* OR "anti-microbial" OR "anti-infective agent" OR antibiotic* OR "anti-biotic") AND TOPIC: (animal* OR livestock* OR herd* OR veterinar* OR poultry OR chicken* OR cow OR calves OR veal* OR beef* OR dairy* OR farm* OR pig). It was used in the same bibliographic databases mentioned earlier. Requests were also sent to all ROADMAP partners to identify reports about interventions and programs aimed at improved AMU.

Because there were not many evaluations of interventions to tackle AMU in animal health, we chose to scan broadly and select articles and reports on unspecific grounds for exclusion and inclusion criteria. Thus, we included studies on any type of intervention that aimed to influence or change AMU and/or decrease AMR and any study that described contextual factors influencing effectiveness, success and adoption of such an intervention and/or concerning the analysis of a regulation as a context or implementation mechanism and/or studies concerning the evaluation or monitoring of an intervention. Articles and reports that described interventions but which did not provide relevant information on the strategy and/or outcomes and/or impacts and/or levers and barriers and/or key factors and/or monitoring of the intervention were excluded from the analysis. Articles and reports describing general guidelines or recommendations on AMU were also excluded.

At the end of the different PRISMA stages, twenty-six articles were eligible for analysis. An additional article (Rademacher et al. 2019) from the first query was added to this list. Figure 1 shows the PRISMA diagram.

Figure 1: The PRISMA diagram

3.2 Summary of findings on initiatives to change AMU

Even though the 27 articles reviewed were not proper impact assessment studies, we present the summary of their content based on a canvass similar to those used in impact assessments studies. We therefore included a description of the context of the interventions, the type of strategies used to change AMU, the actors involved, the monitoring methods and indicators used and the outcomes (and potentially impacts) produced or expected by the intervention.

3.2.1 Interventions' context

The largest number of studies were from Europe (17 out of 27 studies, with Denmark and France having the largest number of studies) followed by Asia (5 studies) (see details in [Appendix 1](#)). Some articles dealt with the same intervention. There were three cross-country studies, all in Europe and including at least four countries. All other studies were conducted in a single-country setting.

Most of the studies were non-specific of a type of production (11 out of 27, see details in [Appendix 2](#)). For interventions set in a particular production system, the majority dealt with the dairy farming system, followed by pig production.

In these different intervention settings there were many contextual factors which could act as levers or barriers to the change in AMU in animal health. The main **levers and motivations** were a **concern for public health** (wanting to decrease the development of AMR in humans) and **market motivations** (maintaining consumers' confidence in the safety of animal products, establishing a product line from herds with no use of antibiotics, or being able to sell products on a specific market). Other levers and motivations included the will to improve animal health management and animal welfare, to change prescribing practices or to have a sense of pride in the service provided.

The **barriers** to AMU change mainly related to a **fear of negative impacts** in terms of productivity, animal health and economy; **uncertainties about** the feasibility, effectiveness and return on investment of **alternatives**; a **lack of knowledge about AMR and its risks** (for both the general public and professionals of animal farming and health); **conflict of interests** (stakeholders with a vested interest in selling AMs, disagreements between the human and animal health sectors) and a **complex position of veterinarians** (pressure to prescribe critical AMs, competition between practices, difficulty to provide unbiased advice to farmers). Other obstacles to AMU change pertained to **insufficiently regulated AM drug distribution**, a **lack of structures and resources for AM stewardship and AMU/AMR monitoring**, **unfavourable ecological and epidemiological contexts** (with high connectivity between human, livestock, and wildlife populations, and high incidence of infectious diseases), **the cost of microbiological testing** and **poor national coordination** and ambition.

These two lists inform about the potential levers on which we can act to lead to the change and the potential barriers to overcome and to take into account during the design of strategies and measures to improve AMU and reduce AMR.

Additional details about the context of each specific intervention among the 27 reviewed articles are provided in [Appendix 3](#).

3.2.2 Types of approaches and strategies

The types of approaches to change AMU differed among the 27 articles. The **tailor-made approach** was the most used and seemed to lead to good results as it aimed to build an individual and specific intervention for each herd. The **participatory approach** was also frequently mentioned and presented similar advantages. Several interventions were designed according to a **One Health approach**, jointly addressing human and animal health aspects.

The **strategies** used for the interventions could be distributed in different categories. Most of them related to:

- **Regulations, norms and standards** : restrictions or bans of use of critical AM, restrictions or bans of use of AM as growth promoters in food animals, regulation and restriction of drug sales and distribution, guidelines for veterinary prescription and therapeutic AMU, penalties for high AMU
- **Knowledge improvement** : training, communication, individual support, feedback reports, awareness campaigns
- **AM stewardship** : involving farmers and veterinarians in the decision-making and design of health plans and policies, diagnostic support programs, antibiograms
- **Animal health and herd management** : prevention practices, promoting good sanitation and hygiene, alternative measures related to feeding or watering, vaccination, internal or external biosecurity, disease control plan, and reducing risky practices
- **Technological innovations** : tape measures and dosage charts to estimate dosage based on livestock body size, thermometers to enable milk pasteurization
- **Monitoring support** : surveillance systems and monitoring of AMU and/or AMR

Many interventions consisted of a combination of different strategies. Some articles mentioned the fact that in a particular context it was not possible to implement some strategies. For example, penalty systems for high AMU, proposals to decrease consumer demand by increasing antibiotic prices or governing AMR through the engagement of citizens and civil society were not considered as possible solutions in some contexts.

Additional details about the type of strategy for each specific intervention are provided in [Appendix 4](#).

3.2.3 Actors involved, influential and impacted

Impact assessment studies of interventions classify actors in three non-exclusive categories: **actors directly involved** in the intervention, **actors who can have an influence** (positive and/or negative) on the process of the intervention, and **actors impacted** (positively and/or negatively) by the intervention.

These distinctions were not made in the reviewed articles since the reviewed articles did not correspond to proper impact assessment studies. However, we tried to extract information on the actors from the 27 articles and classify them accordingly.

Most interventions on AMU change were at the initiative of governments or research institutes. **Actors involved** in the intervention most commonly included **veterinarians** (sometimes also advisors), **farm**

workers (either farm managers, farm owners, herd managers, or animal health workers) and **researchers** or other staff involved in study investigation. Other actors who could be involved in the interventions included community members, children, doctors or feed advisors.

It was more difficult to sort out actors that were influential and impacted. All actors involved in the intervention (researchers, veterinarians and farmers) had some degree of influence and veterinarians and farmers could be impacted. **The drug and food industry** also had an influence on the process and could be impacted by the changes. Various **government bodies** were mentioned who could have an influence including Ministries of Agriculture (or Food and Forestry, Food Agriculture and Fisheries, Environment and Food), Ministries of Industry and Trade, Ministries of Health, Ministries of Education and Governmental pharmaceutical organization. Other actors mentioned included association of farmers, National levy board, hospitals, health centres, healthcare institutions, laboratories, food inspection laboratories, international organizations (FAO, WHO), civil society organizations, distributors of AM products, private animal production companies and agricultural publication companies.

3.2.4 Monitoring and evaluation

Monitoring and evaluation systems are essential to make sure that interventions are well implemented and contribute to satisfactory outcomes and impacts. Several articles provided information on the monitoring system they used. What was monitored, depending on the study, were “results”, “effects”, “outputs”, “changes”, “outcomes”, “compliance”, “efficacy”, “impacts”. However, these terms were sometimes used interchangeably and did not correspond to the standard definitions used in proper impact assessment studies. The proper definitions are as follows:

- **Outputs:** They consist of the **products** resulting from the intervention. They can take the form of scientific or non-scientific knowledge, professional or academic training, expertise, technology, network or other forms of products
- **Outcomes:** they consist of the appropriation of an intervention outputs by actors of the food and drug supply chains, leading to **changes in behaviours, practices** (socioeconomic or technical), and/or **knowledge, capacities and motivations**, and/or **organisations/interactions**
- **Impacts:** they consist of the **long-term effects**, positive or negative, intended or unintended, direct or indirect, induced by an intervention. The impacts are **what remains after the intervention is completed**. Impacts can be of different types: economic, social, territorial, environmental, political, health-related, etc.

Different actors could be involved in the monitoring-evaluation of interventions. **Most of them were farmers, veterinarians and researchers**, and sometimes facilitators and Regional Veterinary and Food Control Authorities. For some interventions, laboratories had a role in the collection and analysis of biological data used for monitoring.

Several monitoring means and data/indicators were used. Very often, **the monitoring process was based on several visits on the farms and intermediate phone calls or meetings**. Different means were used to collect data:

- Questionnaires, online surveys, semi-structured interviews
- On farm observations

- On-farm databases implemented specifically or not for the intervention and which needed support and/or software
- Reports: economic report, annual reports on antibiotic sales, farm-level AMU reports
- Existing networks/database on the results of antibiotic susceptibility tests or on prescribed veterinary medicines or from private milk recording or farming organizations

Box 1 shows the different data and some associated indicators used to monitor interventions. Some data were assessed by scoring and ranking.

Box 1: Data and indicators used for monitoring AMU/AMR interventions

- **AMU on farm:**
Use of critically important antibiotic, antimicrobial and feed consumption, treatment incidence, number of treatments
- **Prescription medicines used and sales:** in pharmacies, feed mills, and veterinary clinics
- **Technical performance (production data):**
Mortality, reproduction, average daily gain, feed conversion rate, milk yield and average lactation number
- **Animal health data:**
Welfare, disease incidence, clinical mastitis incidence, foodborne disease incidence, milk somatic cell score
- **Use of innovation and alternatives:**
Openness to innovation
- **Economic indicators:**
Cost-effectiveness, economic value of changes in technical performance (costs due to disease and productivity; reduced costs in antimicrobials), change in margin over feed cost combined with the direct net cost of the intervention and the change in antimicrobial expenditures to estimate the change in net farm profit
- **Bacterial isolates, food or faecal samples:**
Residues and occurrence of AMR in indicator bacteria, zoonotic bacteria, and pathogenic bacteria from animals, food, and humans
- **Changes in attitudes and behaviours** regarding antibiotic use
- **Grasp of public health messages and knowledge on AMU/AMR**
- **Quality of the intervention:**
Implementation of the activity plan, quality of the animal health planning process (aspects related to preparation for the consultation and quality of the collaboration with the advisory team), accomplishment of the objectives, level of compliance with the intervention

Depending on the kind of data collected, different means of analysis were used (for example isolates analysis for fecal samples, temporal trend analysis for AM prescriptions, statistical comparison between farms exposed and not exposed to the intervention, thematic analysis, etc). In some cases, historical data (i.e., before intervention) were available and compared with observational data (i.e., after intervention) to assess the outcomes and impacts of interventions.

Additional details about the monitoring-evaluation system of each specific intervention are provided in [Appendix 5](#).

3.2.5 Outcomes and impacts

The interventions described in the 27 reviewed articles had goals they wanted to reach. Most commonly, these goals corresponded to **outcomes they wanted to generate** (changes by actors involved in the intervention) and sometimes, these goals also included **impacts they hoped to contribute to** (long-term changes that may go beyond the actors involved in the intervention).

The expected outcomes were of two different kinds: changes in practice, attitudes and interactions or changes in knowledge, capacities and motivations. They are reviewed in Box 2.

The expected impacts are reviewed in Box 3. Some interventions aimed to avoid undesirable impacts such as compromising animal health and welfare and negative economic impacts.

Box 2: Expected outcomes through interventions

Expected outcomes

- A decreased/improved/responsible/rationalised AMU and AM prescribing
- Use of alternatives that reduce and where possible, eliminate the need for AM therapies
- Increased actors' knowledge and awareness
- Improved farmers' perception of a vaccine
- Producers work with their veterinarians to assess and address disease risk regularly
- Staff engaged in using AM are responsible or are adequately supervised

Box 3: Expected impact through interventions

Expected impacts

- To tackle excessive AMU (also in other productions systems and in other countries)
- To promote AM stewardship or to get a genuine sense of stakeholder ownership
- To develop the surveillance of AM consumption
- To stop or limit the emergence, acquisition, transmission dissemination of AMR
- To strengthen the monitoring and evaluation of AMR
- To preserve the effectiveness of AMs
- To improve or maintain animal health, udder health
- To maintain the same herds' production levels
- To reach plan's long-term efficacy and sustainability
- To better understand how participatory approaches with farmers can be successfully applied

Outcomes actually generated by the interventions are reviewed in Box 4. Most of the changes were related to behaviour/practices and consisted of a **reduction or improvement of AMU**. Other important changes related to increased knowledge and awareness, or the use of an innovation, or a new actor's role. In several instances, expected outcomes were not reached (for example veterinarians did not use antibiograms before AM prescription and farmers did not significantly improve their practices).

Regarding **impacts that the interventions contributed to** (reviewed in Box 5), impacts in terms of AMR containment often remained unclear and were mostly seen in animals but not in humans. Economic impacts were very often addressed but costs and benefits were complex to measure and could be compensated by other benefits in the long term.

It is also important to notice that some **unexpected and undesirable outcomes and impacts** were generated through interventions (see Box 6). For example, impacts on animal health, productivity and economic could be positive but also negative. Reducing AMU could increase disease problems and therefore generate an increase of AMU as a partial reversal of the preceding changes.

Box 4: Generated outcomes through interventions

Generated outcomes

- Vets/farmers changed in attitude, behaviour and practices
- A decrease/improvement in AMU prescription, treatment or feeding/AM growth promoters measured by a decrease of: exposure of AM, AM expenditures, treatment incidence, Somatic Cell Score, total mg of antibiotic used per Population Corrected Unit, average Daily Defined Dose of antibiotic, treatment intensity
- Farmers changed their farming management focusing more on biosecurity
- Use of technical innovations
- Changes in AMU policy that reduced the combinations and amounts of AM used to treat calves
- Veterinarians became advisors
- Changes in knowledge, awareness and perception
- A good average farm compliance with the intervention plan
- Veterinary pharmaceutical companies obtain approval for new indications within existing AM classes

Box 5: Impacts to which interventions contributed

Generated positive impact or absence of negative impacts

- Economic impact: higher economic performance, decrease of the net costs per animal produced, increase of net farm profit
- Positive effects or absence of negative effects on production parameters/farm technical performance (mortality, daily weight gain, milk yield, lactation, feed conversion, etc.)
- Positive effects or absence of negative effects on animal health (decrease of disease/infection incidence rates, decrease of Somatic Cell Score)
- Increase of consumers' confidence in meat and meat consumption
- Increase of the acceptance of new measures
- Influence and impacts for better AMU in other countries
- Long-term changes in the AMU after the intervention
- Implementation of the intervention by other actors or in other herds
- A declining trend in AMR

Box 6: Undesirable generated outcomes and impacts

Negative impacts and undesirable outcomes

- Increase of the mortality and disease after intervention
- Increase in therapeutic AMU to control disease
- Increase in the amount of injectable and water-soluble antibiotics used
- Limit of commercialisation opportunities for the veterinary pharmaceutical industry and veterinarians deprived of new tools to meet animal health and welfare needs
- Food companies or retailers have developed strict corporate antibiotic use (or non-use) policies that now dictate production practices
- Negative impact on the country economy

Additional details about the outcomes and impacts of each specific intervention are provided in [Appendix 6](#).

3.3 Limitations of the review

Our review had various limitations. For articles identified through bibliographical databases, we restricted ourselves to articles written in French and English. There were articles available in other languages which seemed relevant to our search (based on English abstracts) but that were not considered because of time and resource constraints for our study. Some articles not available in open-access were also not considered for the same reasons. Our second round of search to palliate for the scarcity of proper impact assessment studies included the terms “intervention*”, “program*”, “planning*”, “plan”, and “polic*”. We may have missed some articles by not including more terms related to “intervention” in the research equation.

Regarding the grey literature, it proved difficult to identify reports other than general guidelines or strategies. A lot of initiatives in terms of changing AMU are led by farmers’ cooperatives or by private groups (including farming but also food distribution groups) and some initiatives are deployed at a very local scale (including only one or a few farms). In such cases, access to information on the strategies and outcomes can be tricky because it is not publicly available and/or because people are reluctant to divulge information that may be used by competitors. More time and resources may have helped identify such reports.

This literature review provides a first overview of the existing evidence but further research is needed. A larger scoping review is planned. More terms have to be included in the search equation and the methodology flaws have to be overcome by rigorously applying PRISMA guidelines for scoping reviews. Further analysis would also be interesting to understand the underpinning theory of change and impact pathways.

4 Conclusion

The success of an intervention and the achievement of desired outcomes and impacts depend on multiple contextual factors. This literature review based on 27 articles allowed us to identify the levers that can be activated and the obstacles that need to be overcome before building interventions. It also provided information on the actors to take into account, the strategies that can be put in place, and finally, the outcomes and impacts that can be measured and monitored over time and the indicators used.

Despite the diversity of contexts and types of interventions on AMU reviewed, we can identify some **key success factors for acceptance and successful change** (Box 7) and **failure factors** that prevent sustainable change and lead actors to revert to previous behaviours once the intervention ends (Box 8).

Box 7: Key success factors of the interventions

Key success factors

- Good collaboration and open discussions among stakeholders
- Tradition of using and respecting science
- Access to all relevant data and samples that were already systematically collected from animals, food, and humans
- Use of participatory and tailor-made (farm-specific) approaches
- Preliminary study to assess the risk perceived by the farmer who undertakes AMU reduction
- An accurate diagnosis of the main herd health problems and underlying causes
- Make sure the farmer is ready to engage in the process (motivation, trust in his/her veterinarian, availability)
- Ownership in animal health planning on dairy farms
- Cooperative systems where the farms own the full production system
- A limited number of objectives
- Advance planning, precise and adapted communication, and demonstration of the measure's legitimacy
- The herd sanitary situation is under control (no major infection, good external biosecurity level)
- Effectiveness of delivery channels of the program
- Identifying potential negative impacts upstream in order to plan specific strategies to avoid them
- Procedure to be followed in case clinical signs reoccur in spite of the implementation of control measures (e.g. using a dosing pump)
- Monitoring system to allow the readjustment of strategies and the sustainability of changes
- Effective AMR surveillance

Box 8: Failure factors of the interventions

Failure factors

- Dilapidated state of the buildings and associated environmental problems
- Persistence of underlying health problems
- Failure of previous attempts
- Lack of alternative options
- Social norms, incentives and structures that drive misuse of medicines almost always remain unchanged

We hope this information will be useful for stakeholders who want to set up interventions for more prudent AMU in animal health.

5 References

- Afema, Josephine A., Margaret A. Davis, et William M. Sicho. 2019. " Antimicrobial Use Policy Change in Pre-Weaned Dairy Calves and Its Impact on Antimicrobial Resistance in Commensal Escherichia Coli: A Cross Sectional and Ecological Study ". *Bmc Microbiology* 19 (1): 217. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12866-019-1576-6>.
- Alvarez S., Jost C.C., Schuetz T., Förch W., Schubert C., and Kristjanson P. (2014). Lessons in Theory of Change from the introductory training on Theories of Change, Impact Pathways and Monitoring & Evaluation, CCSL Learning Brief 10, 4 p., <https://cgspace.cgiar.org/handle/10568/52992>.
- Banerjee A.V., and Duflo E (2009). The experimental approach to development economics. *Annu. Rev. Econ.* 1.1: 151-178.

- Barret D., Blundo-Canto G., Dabat M-H., Devaux-Spatarakis A., Faure G., Hainzelin E., Mathé S., Temple L., Toillier A., Triomphe B., and Vall E. (2018). *ImpresS ex post. Methodological guide to ex post impact evaluation of agricultural research in developing countries*. Montpellier, France, CIRAD, 96 p. ISBN: 978-2-87614-736-2. <https://doi.org/10.19182/agritrop/00006>
- Bennedsgaard, T.W., I.C. Klaas, et M. Vaarst. 2010. "Reducing use of antimicrobials - Experiences from an intervention study in organic dairy herds in Denmark ". *Livestock Science* 131: 183-192. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.livsci.2010.03.018>.
- Blundo Canto, Genowefa, Danielle Barret, Guy Faure, Etienne Hainzelin, Christelle Monier, et Bernard Triomphe. 2018. *ImpreS Ex Ante. An Approach for Building Ex Ante Impact Pathways*. Cirad. <https://doi.org/10.19182/agritrop/00013>.
- Borne, B.H.P. van den, F.J.S. van Soest, M. Reist, et H. Hogeveen. 2017. "Quantifying preferences of farmers and veterinarians for national animal health programs: The example of bovine mastitis and antimicrobial usage in Switzerland ". *Frontiers in Veterinary Science* 4 (JUN). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2017.00082>.
- Breen, J. E., B. Jones, B. Jones, N. Jones, M. Jones, et R. Edwards. 2017. "Implementation of the AHDB Dairy Mastitis Control Plan to Reduce Clinical Mastitis Rate and Antibiotic Use in a Large Dairy Herd ". Édité par B. Pocknee. 2017 British Mastitis Conference, 15, novembre, 31-42.
- Carrique-Mas, J.J., et J. Rushton. 2017. "Integrated interventions to tackle antimicrobial usage in animal production systems: The ViParc project in Vietnam ". *Frontiers in Microbiology* 8 (JUN). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2017.01062>.
- Clémence, B., N. Fortané, D. Calavas, A. Leblond, et É. Gay. 2018. "Why do veterinarians ask for antimicrobial susceptibility testing? A qualitative study exploring determinants and evaluating the impact of antibiotic reduction policy ". *Preventive Veterinary Medicine* 159: 123-134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2018.09.009>.
- Collineau, L., C. Rojo-Gimeno, A. Léger, A. Backhans, S. Loesken, E.O. Nielsen, M. Postma, et al. 2017. "Herd-specific interventions to reduce antimicrobial usage in pig production without jeopardising technical and economic performance ". *Preventive Veterinary Medicine* 144: 167-178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2017.05.023>.
- Collineau, L., Parcheminal, R., Zeller, S., Belloc, C., 2016. What are the key factors for an intervention to reduce antimicrobial usage in pig production to be successful? [French]. *Journées de la Recherche Porcine en France* 313-318.
- Debaere, P.O. 2016. "Ecoantibio: First plan for the reduction of the risks of antibiotic resistance in veterinary medicine (2012-2016) ". *Bulletin de l'Académie Vétérinaire de France* 169 (3): 186-189. <https://doi.org/10.4267/2042/61876>.
- Degeling, C., J. Johnson, J. Iredell, K.-A. Nguyen, J.M. Norris, J.D. Turnidge, A. Dawson, S.M. Carter, et G.L. Gilbert. 2018. "Assessing the public acceptability of proposed policy interventions to reduce the misuse of antibiotics in Australia: A report on two community juries ". *Health Expectations* 21 (1): 90-99. <https://doi.org/10.1111/hex.12589>.
- Devaux-Spatarakis A. (2014). L'évaluation "basée sur la théorie", entre rigueur scientifique et contexte politique." *Politiques et management public* 31.1 : 51-68.
- Dijk, L. van, A. Hayton, D.C.J. Main, A. Booth, A. King, D.C. Barrett, H.J. Buller, et K.K. Reyher. 2017. "Participatory Policy Making by Dairy Producers to Reduce Anti-Microbial use on Farms ". *Zoonoses and Public Health* 64 (6): 476-484. <https://doi.org/10.1111/zph.12329>.

- Hammerum, A.M., O.E. Heuer, H.-D. Emborg, L. Bagger-Skjøt, V.F. Jensen, A.-M. Rogues, R.L. Skov, et al. 2007. " Danish integrated antimicrobial resistance monitoring and research program ". *Emerging Infectious Diseases* 13 (11): 1632-1639.
- Hardefeldt, Laura Y. 2018. " Implementing Antimicrobial Stewardship Programmes in Veterinary Practices ". *Veterinary Record* 182 (24): 688-90. <https://doi.org/10.1136/vr.k2563>.
- Ivemeyer, S., Smolders, G., Brinkmann, J., Gratzner, E., Hansen, B., Henriksen, B.I.F., Huber, J., Leeb, C., March, S., Mejdell, C., Roderick, S., Stöger, E., Vaarst, M., Whistance, L.K., Winckler, C., Walkenhorst, M., 2012. Effects of health and welfare planning on the use of antibiotics and udder health in European dairy farms, in: *Udder Health and Communication*. pp. 69-76. https://doi.org/10.3920/978-90-8686-742-4_5
- Jensen, V.F., de Knecht, L.V., Andersen, V.D., Wingstrand, A., 2014. Temporal relationship between decrease in antimicrobial prescription for Danish pigs and the "Yellow Card" legal intervention directed at reduction of antimicrobial use. *Preventive Veterinary Medicine* 117, 554-564. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2014.08.006>
- Joly P. B., Colinet L., Gaunand A., Lemarié S., and Matt M. (2016). Agricultural research impact assessment: issues, methods and challenges. "Agricultural research impact assessment: Issues, methods and challenges", OECD Food, Agriculture and Fisheries Papers, No. 98, OECD Publishing, Paris. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/5339e165-en>
- Moher, D., Liberati, A., Tetzlaff, J., Altman, D. G., & Prisma Group. (2009). Preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses: the PRISMA statement. *PLoS med*, 6(7), e1000097.
- Morton S. (2015). Progressing research impact assessment: A 'contributions' approach. *Research Evaluation*, 24(4), 405-419.
- Pawson R., and Tilley N (1997). An introduction to scientific realist evaluation. *Evaluation for the 21st century: A handbook* : 405-418.
- Poizat, A., Frappat, B., Corbel, S., Roussel, P., Guenic, M. le, Bonnet-Beaugrand, F., Duval, J., Bareil-le, N., 2018. Learnings from an exploratory implementation of an innovative training-program to reduce antibiotic use in the dairy sector. 13th European International Farming Systems Association (IFSA) Symposium, *Farming systems: facing uncertainties and enhancing opportunities*, 1-5 1-15.
- Rademacher, C. J., Pudenz, C. C., & Schulz, L. L. (2019). Impact assessment of new US Food and Drug Administration regulations on antibiotic use: A post-enactment survey of swine practitioners. *Journal of Swine Health and Production*, 27(4), 210-220. <https://www.aasv.org/shap/issues/v27n4/v27n4p210.pdf>
- Roskam, J.L., Lansink, A.G.J.M.O., Saatkamp, H.W., 2019. The technical and economic impact of veterinary interventions aimed at reducing antimicrobial use on broiler farms. *Poultry Science* 98, 6644-6658. <https://doi.org/10.3382/ps/pez517>
- Roulette, Casey J., Mark A. Caudell, Jennifer W. Roulette, Robert J. Quinlan, Marsha B. Quinlan, Murugan Subbiah, et Douglas R. Call. 2017. " A Two-Month Follow-up Evaluation Testing Interventions to Limit the Emergence and Spread of Antimicrobial Resistant Bacteria among Maasai of Northern Tanzania ". *BMC Infectious Diseases* 17 (1): 770. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12879-017-2857-z>.
- Shryock, T. R. 2012. " Impact Assessment of Risk Management Interventions. (Special Issue: Antimicrobial Resistance in Animal and Public Health.) ". Edited by J. F. Acar and G. Moulin. *Revue Scientifique et Technique - Office International Des Epizooties* 31 (1): 307-315.

- Singh, Shweta Rajkumar, Alvin Qijia Chua, Sok Teng Tan, Clarence C. Tam, Li Yang Hsu, et Helena Legido-Quigley. 2019. " Combating Antimicrobial Resistance in Singapore: A Qualitative Study Exploring the Policy Context, Challenges, Facilitators, and Proposed Strategies ". *Antibiotics* 8 (4): 201. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antibiotics8040201>.
- Speksnijder, D.C., H. Graveland, I.A.J.M. Eijck, R.W.M. Schepers, D.J.J. Heederik, T.J.M. Verheij, et J.A. Wagenaar. 2017. " Effect of structural animal health planning on antimicrobial use and animal health variables in conventional dairy farming in the Netherlands ". *Journal of Dairy Science* 100 (6): 4903-4913. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2016-11924>.
- Stern E., Stame N., Mayne J., Forss K., Davies R., and Befani B. (2012). Broadening the range of designs and methods for impact evaluation. Department for International Development Working paper 38.
- Sun, Qiang, Yang Wang, Anette Hulth, Yonghong Xiao, Lennart E Nilsson, Xuewen Li, Zhenwang Bi, et al. 2018. " Study Protocol for One Health Data Collections, Analyses and Intervention of the Sino-Swedish Integrated Multisectoral Partnership for Antibiotic Resistance Containment (IMPACT) ". *BMJ Open* 8 (1): e017832. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2017-017832>.
- Tangcharoensathien, Viroj, Wanchai Sattayawutthipong, Sukhum Kanjanapimai, Wantanee Kanpravidh, Richard Brown, et Angkana Sommanustweechai. 2017. " Antimicrobial Resistance: From Global Agenda to National Strategic Plan, Thailand ". *Bulletin of the World Health Organization* 95 (8): 599-603. <https://doi.org/10.2471/BLT.16.179648>.
- Thamlikitkul, V., P. Rattanaumpawan, A. Boonyasiri, V. Pumsuwan, T. Judaeng, S. Tiengrim, W. Paveenkittiporn, S. Rojanasthien, S. Jaroenpoj, et S. Issaracharnvanich. 2015. " Thailand Antimicrobial Resistance Containment and Prevention Program ". *Journal of Global Antimicrobial Resistance* 3 (4): 290-294. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jgar.2015.09.003>.
- Wagstrom, Elizabeth A. 2006. " The Take Care Program and Responsible Use of Antibiotics ". *Animal Biotechnology* 17 (2): 233-238. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10495390600957225>.
- Wielinga, Peter R., Vibeke F. Jensen, Frank M. Aarestrup, et Jorgen Schlundt. 2014. " Evidence-Based Policy for Controlling Antimicrobial Resistance in the Food Chain in Denmark ". *Food Control* 40 (juin): 185-192. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2013.11.047>.

6 Appendices

Appendix 1: Countries of the 27 reviewed interventions

Country by region	Number of articles
EUROPE	15
Denmark	4
France	4
Netherlands	1
Switzerland	1
United Kingdom	2
Belgium+France+Germany+Switzerland	1

Austria+Denmark+Germany+Netherlands+Norway+Switzerland	1
9 european anonymized countries	1
ASIA	5
China	1
Singapore	1
Thailand	2
Vietnam	1
NORTH AMERICA	3
United States	3
OCEANIA	2
Australia	2
AFRICA	1
Tanzania	1
GLOBAL SETTING	1
TOTAL	27

Appendix 2: Production system settings of the interventions

Production system settings	Number of articles
Non-specific livestock farming	11
Conventional dairy farming	4
Organic dairy farming	3
Traditional dairy farming	1
Calves farming	1
Pig farming	5
Conventional broiler farming	1
Small-scale poultry farming	1

Appendix 3: Details about the circumstances of the interventions

Afema et al. 2019: In Washington state, USA, antimicrobials are used in pre-weaned calves to prevent infections. Before the new policy was applied most calves (99,4%) received antimicrobials and 70,4 % received a total of 2-4 treatments. The goal of this study was to assess the effect of antimicrobial use policy changes to reduce resistance and E.coli was used as indicator species.

Bennedsgaard et al. 2010: The development project explicitly focused on dairy producers effort to gradually phase out the use of antimicrobials in their herd. This article refers to several other papers on Stable schools and reduction of antimicrobial use. In this paper data on production and herd health in Denmark were evaluated from two years before until three years after the start of Stable Schools.

Bourelly, 2018: For public health reasons, increasing attention had focused on more rational use of antimicrobial in farm animals. This research explored the viewpoint of French veterinarians and the challenges they are facing in the fight against antimicrobial resistance, within the context of changing regulations.

Carrigue-Mas, J.J., et J. Rushton. 2017: The ViParc project has been formulated as a “randomized before-and-after controlled study targeting small-scale poultry farms in the Mekong Delta region of Vietnam.

Collineau et al. 2016: The French action plan for the reduction of the risks of antibiotic resistance in veterinary medicine (Ecoantibio plan 2017) promotes the reduction of antimicrobial usage in pig medicine. However, reducing antimicrobial usage might be perceived as risky by the farmer, especially when it comes to reducing preventive treatments. Once treatments are stopped, farmers may also be tempted to resume them if health problems reappear.

Collineau et al. 2017: Little is known about the feasibility, effectiveness and return on investment of preventive measures to reduce the need for antimicrobial treatments. Herd-specific interventions aimed at reducing antimicrobial usage in pig production while implementing alternative measures.

Debarere et al. 2016: The Ecoantibio plan is the French plan for the reduction of the risk of antibiotic resistance in veterinary medicine. The plan aims to reduce the exposure of animals to antibiotics by 25% in five years and to change the practices of prescribing and use of antibiotics.

Degeling et al. 2017: The public acceptability of proposed policy interventions to reduce the misuse of antibiotics in Australia was assessed by asking two community juries.

Hammerum et al. 2007: The result of having DANMAP (Danish Integrated Antimicrobial Resistance Monitoring and Research program) for eleven years were evaluated.

Hardefeldt et al. 2018: The veterinary profession will need to develop strategies for Antimicrobial Stewardship (AMS). The aim was to gain an in-depth understanding of the factors that influence AMS in Australian Veterinary practices.

Ivemeyer et al. 2012: To improve sustainability of dairy production it is essential to establish concepts to reduce medicine use whilst safeguarding or improving herd health and productivity. The major part of antimicrobial drug use is performed for udder treatments.

Jensen et al 2014: After a decrease of AMU in livestock in Denmark following the Cascade Rule (Executive Order 142/1993), the restriction of veterinarians’ profit from sales of prescription medicines and the 1999 ban of all antimicrobial growth-promoters, AMU increased again continuously from 2003 to 2009, mainly in pigs. Consequently, the Danish Veterinary and Food Administration (DVFA) established the “Yellow Card” intervention (Executive Order 1319/2010).

Poizat et al 2018: Health indicator of good udder health have not improved over the last 18 years in France. In addition, dairy farmers are still regularly using antibiotics in an inappropriate manner during lactating period, and about two third of French dairy farmers could be implementing systematic dry cow therapy. It was hypothesised that improving knowledge and perception of farmers on mastitis prevention and management could improve their practices and their dairy herd health status.

Rademacher et al. 2019: After a 2016 survey of practicing swine veterinarians on Veterinary Feed Directive preparation, this follow-up survey was conducted in 2017 to assess post-enactment impacts of the revised VFD.

Roskam et al. 2019: Farmers' main objection to implement strategies for reducing AMU appear to be mainly financial. Existing studies on the impact of AMU on economic performance have focused on commercial pig production. The possibilities of reducing AMU in broiler production through the application of tailor-made interventions have not been investigated so far.

Roulette et al. 2017: In Northern Tanzania, >95% of Maasai households self-administer antibiotics to their livestock while 75% of these households do so without consulting professional veterinarians or livestock officers. In previous study, many Maasai men expressed concerns about under- and overdosing livestock, and several explicitly requested help in determining correct dosages.

Singh et al. 2019: Singapore has well-functioning stewardship programs, comprehensive hospital surveillance systems, and some of the latest technologies and innovations to address it but difficulties to address AMR. There is an increasing need to address the social, economic, political, cultural, and behavioral aspects influencing AMR rather than just focusing on the technical solutions. Conflicts reported specifically between human and animal health experts.

Speksnijder et al. 2017: In the Netherlands, measures include strict mandatory reduction targets set by the national government combined with private initiatives to accomplish this objective. There is great variation in AMU between farms, indicating that there is room for further improvement on farms with higher than average AMU. Despite many successful efforts to reduce veterinary AMU, on a substantial number of farms it has remained relatively high over the past few years. Farm-specific solutions are required to further lower AMU on these farms.

Sun et al. 2018: China is one of the largest producers and consumers of antibiotics in the world. There is a problem of high prevalence of resistant bacteria among humans and animals. Additionally, information on the epidemiological background in rural China is lacking.

Tangcharoensathien et al. 2017: Thailand has previously addressed AMR with fragmented approaches: antimicrobial resistance formed a small component of the National drug development strategy (2012–2016) and the National strategic plan on emerging infectious disease (2013–2016). Given the high turnover of policy-makers, it may be difficult to sustain policy commitment.

Thamlikitkul et al. 2015: AMR is an urgent threat in Thailand but interventions to contain and prevent AMR have been frequently but not systematically proposed or executed over the past decade. Inappropriate AMU is frequent and consumption of antibiotics that are dispensed by retail shops and drug stores is a driving force for developing AMR.

van den Borne et al. 2017: Bovine udder health in Switzerland is of a relatively high level. However, AMU seems high in comparison to other European countries. A new udder health and AMU improvement program could improve this situation but it is uncertain whether there is support from the field.

van Dijk et al. 2017: Many dairy producers in the UK were already stringent in their AMU. The only UK regulatory measures are voluntary measures to ensure best practice and responsible use through farm assurance schemes and compliance to retailer standards for meat and animal products, as described in the UK Five Year AM Strategy 2013 to 2018. Several major retailers and milk buyers set their own

guidelines regarding AMU. The Responsible Use of Medicines in Agriculture (RUMA) Alliance (organizations along the value chain, including farmer representative organizations, retailers, veterinary practices, farm assurance organizations and animal welfare organizations) published guidelines for more responsible AMU by cattle farmers.

Wagstrom 2006: In 2002 the US National Pork Board issued a Board Statement on Antimicrobial use in Pork Production which urged all producers take appropriate steps to decrease the need for the application of antimicrobials.

Wielinga et al. 2014: There is a fear of negative economic effect because farming industry in Denmark is of socio-economic importance and AMU is economically beneficial for industries, vets (direct sales) and farmers secondly. Human and animal health authorities and the farmers recognized lack of knowledge about the zoonotic risk of AMR and they were surprised by the high level of AMR in food animals. Therefore, the Danish farmer associations agreed to a voluntary withdrawal of avoparcin use in chickens.

Appendix 4: Details about the strategies of the interventions

Afema et al. 2019: New treatment policy was implemented to reduce AMR. The goal was to improve calf health and promote antimicrobial stewardship. Based on feedback and interaction between study investigators, farm management and consulting veterinarians, the first treatment of calves was reduced in two steps from using three different treatments in May 2016 to the use of two treatments in August and only one treatment to newborn calves in September.

Bennedsgaard et al. 2010: The concept of the project was to reduce or phase out the need for antimicrobial treatments through herd health and welfare promotion and avoid unnecessary use of antimicrobials. To be able to do so the farmers from 23 Danish organic dairy farms participated in Stable School Farmer groups from February 2004 to March 2005 in order to go through a common learning and development process toward their common goal.

Bourelly, 2018: The impact of a French decree (2016) requiring an antibiogram before the use of certain critically antimicrobial agents was evaluated. Use of antibiograms in veterinary medicine was multifactorial, 46 factors grouped into 11 categories were identified.

Breen et al. 2017: The AHDB Dairy Mastitis Control Plan (DMCP) in the UK and was rolled out to more 1000 herds between 2009 and 2012.

Carrique-Mas, J.J., et J. Rushton. 2017: The ViParc project aims to provide farmers with a locally-adapted veterinary support service to help them reduce their reliance on antimicrobials. ThViParc project integrates socio-economic analysis that will provide insights into the drivers of antimicrobial usage as well as an assessment of the cost-effectiveness of the proposed intervention.

Collineau et al 2016: Tailor-made interventions (formulated by the veterinarian and discussed with the farmer) were defined for each herd and aimed at i) reducing antimicrobial usage, especially preventive group treatments (e.g. discontinuation of routine lincomycin and colistin administration in post-wean-

ing period, of systematic injection of amoxicillin at castration, of preventive oxytetracycline administration to sows, of colistin and doxycycline supplementation in 1st age formula, etc) and ii) implementing alternative strategies to antimicrobial treatments. Alternative measures could relate to feeding or watering (e.g. distribution of the first age food in 2 daily meals instead of 4 previously), vaccination (e.g. against oedema disease caused by Shiga toxin Stx2e-producing *Escherichia coli*), internal or external biosecurity (e.g. deratting 6 times a year instead of 4 times a year previously), or other animal health management measures (e.g. better acclimatization of gilts through adaptation to the microbiome in quarantine, then at 6 and 3 weeks before farrowing).

Collineau, 2017: An intervention study was conducted in 70 farrow-ti-finish pig farms located in Belgium, France, Germany and Sweden. Herd specific interventions were defined together with the farmer and the herd veterinarian.

Debarere 2016: Commitment and mobilization of veterinarians with farmers.

Degeling et al. 2017: The juries were convened for 1-3 days, they were asked to consider the specific issues, they heard evidence and they were given time for deliberation, and to come to a conclusion.

Hammerum et al. 2017: DANMAP is a cooperation between veterinary and human healthcare providers. This integrated program was made possible because access to all relevant data and samples that were already systematically collected from animals, food, and humans has been shared.

Hardefeldt et al. 2018: A questionnaire to assess veterinarians attitude to AMR called: explanatory mixed methods design was used.

Ivemeyer et al 2012: Animal health and welfare planning (AHWP) was carried out either in farmer field schools or using one-to-one-advice. The AHWP process was not standardized across all countries, but the overall AHWP principle was systematically fulfilled, that is : (1) should aim at continuous development and improvement; and (2) should incorporate health promotion and disease handling based on a strategy including (a) investigation of current status and indications (animal based and resource based parameters), (b) evaluation, (c) action and (d) review. The process should (3) be farm specific, (4) guarantee farmer ownership, (5) involve external persons and external knowledge, (6) agree to organic principals, (7) acknowledge good aspects and (8) include a written plan based on the farmer's conclusions or action points.

Jensen et al 2014: The Yellow Card intervention was designed to target pig farmers using high amounts of antimicrobials per pig. Usage thresholds are dynamic; initially thresholds were set at twice the average use in herds of any of the three production age groups. In July 2010, farmers with herds above the 80th percentile received a letter, warning them that they were close to Yellow Card thresholds, and Yellow Cards were issued from December 2010 onwards. A Yellow Card initially releases an order to reduce AMU below the threshold within nine months. If this target is not reached, a second-opinion veterinarian is involved to develop a strategy for reduction. Further measures include quarterly visits from the authority.

Poizat et al 2018: Innovative training program: one classroom-training day, virtual classrooms, and an individual support with the farmer. Two groups of farmers addressed two different themes, depending on their herds' udder health: (i) improvement of mastitis prevention during lactation for herds experiencing frequent clinical mastitis, and (ii) implementation of selective dry cow therapy for herds with good udder health, instead of implementing blanket dry cow therapy.

Rademacher et al 2019: Strategy left to each veterinarian's discretion. More visits, elimination or decrease of antibiotics for growth promotion (or move to non-medically important growth promotants), increased vaccinations and non-antibiotic feed additives, modified biosecurity and nutrition, etc.

Roskam et al 2019: The type of interventions was defined in a farm specific action plan aimed at reducing AMU. About 51.26% of the interventions undertaken targeted the animals (i.e., disease management), 19.33% of the interventions targeted the farmer, and 29.41% targeted the farm (i.e., farm management). Interventions were mainly addressing coccidiosis, feed, and training of the farmer.

Roulette et al. 2017: [Intervention based on a previous qualitative, ethnographic, interviews study.] A collaborative, culturally-situated, community-level public health intervention project aiming at reducing selection and transmission of E. coli bacteria by providing knowledge of AMR and innovations to facilitate pasteurization and correct antibiotic dosage. Maasai individuals were provided with health messages to increase awareness and knowledge of bacteria and AMR, and training and materials for two technological innovations to facilitate the prudent use of veterinary antibiotics: (1) tape measures and dosage charts to estimate dosage based on livestock body size; and (2) thermometers to enable milk pasteurization. Conclusion of the evaluation : To effectively reduce selection for AMR in agropastoral communities, different health-innovation promotion strategies will be needed for men and women.

Shryock 2012: [Impact assessment of different interventions] The Codex Alimentarius Code of Practice for the responsible AMU and the OIE Terrestrial Animal Health Code contain guidelines for the responsible AMU in food-producing animals that include recommendations : a general risk assessment pathway to develop regulatory risk assessment guidelines, Veterinary International Cooperation on harmonization (VICH) Guideline 27, which is a general evaluation (not a risk assessment) of the potential for antimicrobial resistance to be selected by a particular product.

Singh et al. 2019: [Contextual and qualitative study] In line with the WHO Global Action Plan for AMR, Singapore launched its own One Health multisectoral National Strategic Action Plan on AMR to reduce the emergence and spread of drug-resistant microorganisms through five core strategies: (1) Surveillance and risk assessment; (2) Research; (3) Education; (4) Prevention and control of infection; and (5) Optimization of antimicrobial use. Suggestions of strategy: the agricultural sector in Singapore is small and the availability of adequate veterinary expertise limited; imposing tight regulations on antibiotic access in the absence of qualified prescribers is therefore challenging, and persuasive strategies to reduce antibiotic use in this sector are likely to be more realistic, at least in the short term. Governing AMR through the engagement of citizens and civil society was not reported as a strategy in Singapore. The most important strategies suggested by participants to combat AMR and to raise awareness among the population: the need to project AMR costs to draw more attention to the topic; pushing forward the AMR agenda by fear of no treatment; creating a community of practice; considering the social aspects of AMR in order to develop prevention efforts against AMR; engaging the community and public campaigns on the drivers of AMR; and increasing vaccination rates in children and adult population.

Speksnijder et al. 2017: A facilitated approach to animal health planning program in conventional dairy farming. Reducing the burden of animal diseases at the farm level by means of a structured approach to animal health planning could be promising. Farm-specific solutions are required to further lower AMU on these farms. Process: 1. Preparation phase: course on advisory and communication skills for vet, e-learning on structural animal health planning for farmers and feed advisers and participants all

individually described their own view on the current performance and points for improvements related to animal health. 2. Intake farm visit under facilitation: development of their own animal health plan. Specific, measurable, acceptable, realistic, and timely (SMART) objectives were set, priorities were chosen, and action points were planned and summarized in an activity plan sent to the participants. Feedbacks have been provided to improve collaboration in the future. 3. Two follow-ups at 4 and 8 months, by telephone and e-mail to remind about the activity plan, monitor progress in the implementation of the action points according to the timetable in the action plan, and support advisory teams that encountered difficulties in the implementation. 4. Evaluation process and readjustment phase: after 1 year, a final farm visit with the facilitator was planned and the advisory team have to develop the animal health plan for the coming year.

Sun et al. 2018: [Preliminary FGD with rural residents to understand attitudes and knowledge] The Sino-Swedish Integrated Multisectoral Partnership for Antibiotic Resistance Containment (IMPACT) is a cross-sectoral and integrated project on antibiotic resistance to address gaps in current knowledge and seeks to improve the situation through a system wide intervention. One Health and holistic approach. Process: (1) Joint problem formulation around a One Health approach to antibiotic resistance including development of shared and harmonised method protocols; (2) A baseline situation analysis, investigating the present situation of knowledge, attitudes, practices and perceptions on antibiotic use and antibiotic resistance across human, animal and environment sectors; (3) Design and implementation of a multifaceted context-specific intervention to prevent infections, improve antibiotic use in humans and animals, and limit the spread of resistant bacteria; (4) Evaluation of the intervention through a repeated data collection and situation analysis. The initial results from the baseline data collection in the community were used to design a contextually appropriate and sustainable One Health intervention package included training for village doctors and veterinarians; for village residents, there are lectures, educational posters, booklets and educational audio tapes.

Tangcharoensathien et al. 2017: First National strategic plan on AMR in Thailand included six strategic actions and five targets. A One Health national system for the surveillance of antimicrobial consumption. Recommendation: strong political commitment, national ownership and adequate multisectoral institutional capacities will be essential for the effective implementation of the national plan.

Thamlikitkul et al. 2015: The Thailand Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR) Containment and Prevention Program to develop, co-ordinate and implement AMR Containment and Prevention (AMRCP) operational actions in Thailand following the 'One Health' approach to stop producing AMR by promoting responsible use of antibiotics, and to stop the acquisition and transmission of AMR by promoting good sanitation and hygiene as well as compliance with infection control and prevention practices.

van den Borne et al. 2017: [Preliminary study] Quantify preferences of dairy farmers and veterinarians for the start and design characteristics of a new national udder health and AMU improvement program in Switzerland. Conclusion about strategy: Farmers and veterinarians were in favor of starting a new voluntary udder health and AMU improvement program for all dairy herds programs without penalty system for high AMU but different expected stewardship with the veterinary organization and the government taking the lead in program design decision making.

van Dijk et al. 2017: Participatory and antimicrobial stewardship policy making by dairy producers including practical measures to reduce AMU on farms while maintaining or improving dairy herd health and welfare. Process: workshops to assess perceptions of producers and vet on AMU, to adapt a conceptual model for the policy structure.

Wagstrom 2006: Development of a comprehensive producer education and awareness program focused on the responsible use of antimicrobials in pork production. The “Take Care—Use Antibiotics Responsibly Program” is based on principles and guidelines that provide the producer and veterinarian the basis for antibiotic use decision-making. Process: series of focus groups with pork producers and veterinarians, separately, to explore producer attitudes and current behaviors as they relate to AMU, identify the key influencers for AMU, and to identify the best way to communicate about antibiotics with producers and benchmarking survey with pork producers and swine veterinarians to establish precommunication program benchmark statistics in regard to attitudes, awareness, and behaviour concerning antibiotic usage and practices.

Wielinga et al. 2014: Different legislative measures and organizational strategies: ban of avoparcin as AGP motivated by farmers, creation in 1996 of a new Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Fisheries in charge of the managing the farm-to-fork food chain together with the Ministry of Health, new legislation reducing and fixing the veterinarians profit from the direct sales of antimicrobials, regulation on prescribing and delivering, the Danish integrated antimicrobial resistance monitoring and research program (DANMAP) for evidence based decision making, the Yellow card initiative.

Appendix 5: Details about the monitoring of the interventions

Afema et al. 2019: To monitor the antimicrobial use there was on-farm record system designed to capture antimicrobial use per animal, and the resistance was measured by E. coli as an indicator.

Bennedsgaard et al. 2010: Disease treatment by the veterinarian and the medicine used were reported to the Danish Cattle Database by the veterinarian.

Bourelly, 2018: Semistructured interviews with 66 veterinarians were conducted in France.

Carrique-Mas, J.J., et J. Rushton. 2017: The project was still ongoing when the paper was written, therefore no outcomes nor impacts yet.

Collineau et al 2016: The farms were monitored during one year following the implementation of the intervention plan, during which two intermediate points (by telephone or during a visit) and a final visit were carried out by the investigator and/or the referring veterinarian. In particular, the follow-up aimed to : i) Assess compliance with the measures initially decided upon (rated on a scale of 1 =null to 5=excellent), and, in the case of partial or no compliance, to describe the reasons for little or no implementation of the measures. The scores obtained were then grouped and converted into an overall compliance score for the farm's intervention plan, ranging from 0 (= no measures implemented) to 100 (= all measures fully implemented); ii) Quantify the reduction of antimicrobial usage in terms of treatment incidence (the number of animals per 1000 receiving a daily dose of antibiotics during the period at risk of being treated). For each specialty, the farmer specified for which indication (preventive or curative) and age group the specialty was purchased. When the specialty was purchased for more than one age group, the farmer was asked to estimate the proportion of antibiotics used in each age group.

Collineau, 2017: The 70 farms were followed over one year and their antimicrobial usage and technical performance were compared with values from the year before the intervention.

Degeling et al. 2017: The juries were convened for 1-3 days, they were asked to consider the specific issues, they heard evidence and they were given time for deliberation, and to come to a conclusion.

Hardefeldt et al. 2018: A quantitative phase consisted of an online questionnaire to assess veterinarians attitude to antimicrobial use and a qualitative phase consisted of semistructured interviews to understand the barriers to and enablers of antimicrobial stewardship in veterinary practices In Australia.

Ivemeyer et al 2012: Monitored the number of udder treatments with antibiotics, the somatic cell score (SCS) which served as an indicator of udder health, and milk yield as well as average lactation number which were calculated at farm level from milk recording data. Two visits within a one year interval (during the winter housing period) for the collection of health and welfare data. For treatment records and milk recording data two periods were defined for analysis: year 0 being the period of 365 days before the first visit including the day of the first visit (Y0); year 1 containing the 365 days following the first visit (Y1). Treatment data from AT, DE, NL and CH were based on farm records and veterinary bills, respectively, whereas data from DK and NO originated from national central databases. Treatments per farm were reported as total of cases per cow and year. Milk recording data were obtained from national central databases (DK, NO) or from private milk recording or farming organizations (AT, CH, DE, NL).

Jensen et al 2014: Data on antimicrobial prescription for pigs during 2002–2012 was obtained from the national database on veterinary prescribed medicines, VetStat, which covers more than 99% of the veterinary AMU in Denmark. Descriptive analysis of temporal trends in quantitative antimicrobial prescription for pigs on national level was performed for each administration route, age group and disease group. In addition, prescription patterns of the three most prescribed antimicrobial classes (tetracyclines, macrolides and pleuromutilins) for weaners and finishers were studied at herd level.

Poizat et al 2018: The objective was to evaluate the impact of an innovative training and advisory program focused on improvement of udder health prevention and antibiotic use on farmers' knowledge, perceptions, and practices, as well as its impact on herd health. Used an exposed and non-exposed epidemiological study. The impact of the training program on farmers' knowledge, practices, herd health and antibiotic use was assessed using an adapted form of the process evaluation framework used for complex interventions. The design of the evaluation framework measuring the impact of the training program took into account different elements: knowledge, perception, practices, herd health, antibiotic consumption. Methods used are of qualitative and quantitative nature, allowing evaluating the impact of the whole program with more precision. The epidemiological design allowed for the control of important parameters influencing the results (e.g. the willingness of farmers to follow advice).

Rademacher et al 2019: Paper questionnaire distributed to 125 practicing swine veterinarians attending the 2017 Iowa State University (ISU) James D. McKean Swine Disease Conference held in Ames, Iowa, on November 2-3, 2017 (29 returned a completed survey), and a convenience sample of 35 practicing swine veterinarians from the upper Midwest region of the United States, identified by ISU faculty and staff who were familiar with swine production systems and swine-focused veterinary clinics, and surveyed through Qualtrics online survey (13 returned a completed survey).

Roskam et al 2019 : For each participating farm, historical data (i.e., before intervention) and observational data (i.e., after intervention) were collected on a flock basis. Data were collected with respect to technical performance, such as average daily gain (ADG), feed conversion rate (FCR), mortality (MR),

and AMU. Data on AMU were quantified in a standardized manner by using the treatment incidence (TI) as described by Persoons et al 2012. In addition to the data of the intervention farms, similar data from 13 non-intervention broiler farms were collected. These farms are semi-control farms since no specific action plan was developed nor implemented. However, regular veterinary practices have taken place at these farms. The data of these farms were therefore used to compare the results of the intervention farms with the results of non-intervention farms. The economic impact of on-farm intervention is estimated in 2 different ways. First, by calculating the economic value (EV) of changes in technical performance, and second by assessing the impact on the gross margin.

Roulette et al. 2017: A major aim of this study is to determine the effectiveness of the intervention to provide insight for future community-health interventions. A two-month follow-up evaluation was conducted to evaluate retention of the public health messages and knowledge and innovation use in relation to demographic and socioeconomic variables. Knowledge retention was assessed using open-ended questionnaires (questions to assess knowledge in three domains: 1) bacteria, 2) antibiotic resistance, and, 3) the health benefits of using the innovations). Correct use of the innovations was assessed using behavioral observations in which participants were asked to demonstrate their use of the innovation. During these demonstrations, researchers noted the number of steps performed correctly. The results of this study are complicated by the short duration between intervention and follow-up, which makes it difficult to draw firm conclusions regarding the long-term retention of knowledge and skills but it still bring some ideas of improvements of the intervention.

Shryock 2012: The effectiveness of AMR interventions can be evaluated, in part, by AMR monitoring and antibiotic use sales data or foodborne disease surveillance. This type of survey data is most appropriately applied to evaluating the effectiveness of specific activities. This can range from trends in AMR over time to changes in AMU or sales. Foodborne disease surveillance trends are becoming available but attribution to specific commodities and practices remains a challenge. In reviewing the many AMR risk management interventions that have been described, surprisingly there are no specific success criteria attached to them before implementation. It is necessary to define both the specific actions to be taken by a stakeholder as well as the agreed criteria for success and the means to measure the effect. Although not mentioned as components of the evaluation approach, other measurements appropriate to the interventions should also be described. For example, veterinarian education on clinical practice guidelines could be documented or records of antibiotic use on the farm could be summarised.

Singh et al. 2019: Need for good quality data obtained from standardized surveillance platforms at the national level to reach strategies and follow outcomes.

Speksnijder et al. 2017: After 1 year, the effects of this program on animal health, production parameters, and AMU were evaluated and compared with control farms that did not have a facilitated animal health planning program. The collaboration as a team, the implementation of the activity plan, and the objectives were evaluated. The facilitators assessed the quality of the animal health planning process per farm by assigning a score between 1 (poor) and 5 (good) on 10 variables grouped into 2 scales: aspects concerning preparation for the consultation (5 variables) and quality of the collaboration of the advisory team in the animal health planning process (5 variables). The AMU data at farm level were derived from quarterly farm-level AMU reports (via MediRund) of the integral quality organization of the sector. Farmers in the intervention and control groups provided animal health and production data over the years preceding and during the study period. Most of these data were already available as part of the mandatory annual Farm Health Plan. Additional production and health parameters were derived from the herd improvement companies and dairy collaboration as far as these were available. The level of compliance with the action points and accomplishment of the objectives were rated on a

scale of 0 to 2 to get an idea of the implementation and outcomes, respectively, of the animal health plans.

Sun et al. 2018: Evaluation of the intervention through a repeated data collection and situation analysis. A process evaluation form is completed by the researchers from Shandong University when they monitor the intervention with local partners. Evaluation of implementation process and impacts of intervention in comparison with control village and previous data (before implementation) through questionnaires and isolates analysis.

Thamlikitkul et al. 2015: The process, output, outcome and impact of the Thailand AMRCP operational actions between 2012 and 2016 are monitored according to 10 indicators suggested by the WHO South-East Asia Regional Office. Assessment of implementation of the Thailand AMRCP Program in the selected pilot areas will be made to determine the required resources, benefits, key success factors, obstacles and barriers of implementation to produce a more suitable and efficient package that will subsequently be implemented other districts in Thailand.

Wagstrom 2006: Further assessment of the program is planned by developing pilot farms and measuring changes in attitudes and behaviors regarding antibiotic use on the pilot farms and a follow-up to the benchmarking survey will be conducted at intervals following the initial survey. Not possible to measure changes in antibiotic use or antibiotic resistance due to implementation of the program. Because the program is not a certification or assessment program it will be hard to assess industry compliance with the principles and guidelines.

Wielinga et al. 2014: The Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Fisheries together with the Ministry of Health initiated an integrated surveillance program: the Danish integrated antimicrobial resistance monitoring and research program (DANMAP) and the database VetStat was initiated in 2000 to monitor the veterinarian AMU and effects of the ban and measures. It helped to convince stakeholders, to produce evidence-based legislation and decision-making by transparency, put new emerging AMR risk in political, agriculture, public health agenda.

Appendix 6: Details about the outcomes and impacts of the interventions

Afema et al. 2019: Levels of resistance to most antimicrobials declined over time. The results emphasize the importance of a continuum of recordkeeping, validation of records, feedback of data and active outreach and education as a cornerstone of antimicrobial stewardship on farms. It was concluded that information feedback to farms can influence farm managers to reduce antimicrobial use and this can change endemic farm resistance patterns.

Bennedsgaard et al. 2010: The incidence rate of mastitis treatment was reduced considerably from 20 treatments per 100 cows years to 10 treatments per 100 cows years after the project period. It was concluded that the farmers participating in the Stable Schools managed to reduce the use of antimicrobials in their herds also after the project period without apparent negative effects on production and udder and herd health.

Bourelly, 2018: The use of antibiograms was not increased but there was a change in prescriptions due to field constraints and the time needed to obtain the results of antibiograms. Respondents see the

decree as an aid in promoting responsible and rational use of antibiotics fostering the use of alternatives. The evaluation of the impact of the decree aimed at reducing the use of critically important antibiotics highlights key factors for a successful change in regulations, such as advanced planning, precise abs adapted communication and demonstration of the measurer's legitimacy.

Breen et al. 2017: Implementation of a structured approach to mastitis control reduces intramammary infections and mastitis rate and leads to a reduction in antibiotic use.

Collineau et al 2016: Average herd compliance with the intervention plan was 79% (min: 20%, max: 100%) and led to a significant reduction of antimicrobial usage by 34.9% in sucklers and 50.7% in weaners. Three case studies were also presented to illustrate high, medium and low levels of success of the intervention plans. This study highlighted key factors for the success of a plan to reduce antimicrobial usage: i) make an accurate diagnosis of the main herd health problems and underlying causes, ii) make sure the farmer is ready to engage in the process (motivation, trust in his/her veterinarian, availability), iii) ensure the herd sanitary situation is under control (no major infection, good external biosecurity level), iv) define the procedure to be followed in case clinical signs reoccur in spite of the implementation of control measures (e.g. using a dosing pump) and v) assess the risk perceived by the farmer who undertakes to reduce antimicrobial usage (better follow-up of farmers with higher risk aversion)

Collineau, 2017: A substantial reduction in antimicrobial usage in pig farming could be achieved, without impacting the overall farm technical performance. A median reduction of 47% of antimicrobial usage was obtained.

Debarere 2016: The drop of 20% in four years shows that the plan is about to be reached. This is primarily related to the commitment and mobilization of veterinarians with farmers.

Degeling et al. 2017: Two juries concluded that potential policy interventions should be directed towards: 1. Ensuring that the public and prescribers were better educated about the dangers of antibiotics resistance 2. Making community-based human and animal health-care practitioners accountable for their prescribing decisions. Both juries rejected increasing antibiotic process.

Hammerum et al. 2017: DANMAP has led to changes in the use of antimicrobial agents in Denmark and other countries. In Denmark, it has mostly been seen in animals. Several results are listed in the paper e.i. Ban of Antimicrobial growth promoters, VetStat Monitoring program, new guidelines for veterinary prescription of antimicrobial agents for pigs etc.

Hardefeldt et al. 2018: Key barriers for Antimicrobial Stewardship (AMS): lack of governance structure, client expectations and competition between practices, cost of microbiological testing, and lack of access to education, training and AMS resources. Enablers to AMS: concern for the role of veterinary antimicrobial use in the development of AMR in humans, a sense of pride in the service provided, preparedness to change prescribing practices.

Ivemeyer et al 2012: Udder treatments with antibiotics decreased over all farms ($p=0.004$) and SCS improved significantly over all farms ($p=0.025$), whilst milk yield and average lactation number remained unchanged. Choosing 'udder health' as a focus area in AHWP (58% of the farmers) did not further improve the parameters investigated. Limit: As there were no control farms included in the study, the extent that general public discussion of use of antimicrobials in farm animal production influenced the results remains open.

Jensen et al 2014: A 25% decline in the total AMU per pig produced occurred between 2009 and 2011. A decline was observed both in sows and piglets (31%), weaners (34%) and finishers (19%). Reduced prescription of tetracycline, macrolides and pleuromutilins for oral use, mainly for gastrointestinal disease (GI) in weaners and finishers, explained 76% of the total reduction. In 2012, the overall antimicrobial use increased by 10%, as a partial reversal of the preceding changes in prescription pattern (potential explanations could be increased disease problems; practical and economic disadvantages of other disease control strategies; and/or a result of some farmers resuming some treatment practices from before the Yellow Card announcement. On herd level, the decline and subsequent increase was mainly related to changes in number of herds receiving regular monthly prescriptions. This study demonstrated that the steep decrease in AMU in the Danish pig production was temporally related with the announcement and introduction of the Yellow Card intervention.

Poizat et al 2018: Farmers exposed to the program significantly increased their knowledge and perception whereas the non-exposed farmers did not change their marks between t0 and tf. Farmers' practices implemented to prevent mastitis during milking did not significantly improved during the program. Farmers' practices regarding the use of a sealant did significantly improve for exposed farmers during the duration of the program: more farmers did use sealant at dry-off. Both exposed and non-exposed farmers did improve their practices of antibiotic use at dry-off, which could show a trend in the general population for the improvement of practices at dry-off, animal health and antibiotic use. The duration of the program (one and a half year) was relatively short to observe a change in practices, longer program could provide better results.

Rademacher et al 2019: More than half of 41 survey respondents (24 veterinarians; 58.5%) felt as though they were conducting more site visits per operation with the new VFD regulations. Regarding client recruitment, 17 veterinarians (41.5%) reported being approached by new clients for the purpose of writing VFDs. Fourteen veterinarians (34.1%) accepted new clients that approached them specifically to provide VFDs. Writing and delivering VFDs was the largest annual cost across all respondents with a mean value of \$4051 and a median value of \$3000. The annual cost for maintaining VFD records was similar in expense with a mean value of \$3561 and a median value of \$1000. The lowest annual cost to business operations was training staff on VFD requirements (mean of \$787; median of \$500). The largest percentage of responding veterinarians (9 of 20; 22.5%) indicated a 21% to 30% perceived reduction in the use of antibiotics in feed by their clients as a result of the new antibiotic regulations. Thirteen (32.5%) respondents perceived a 51% to 100% reduction of antibiotic use in feed among their clients. Swine veterinarians also reported a perceived increase in the amount of injectable (19 of 40 respondents; 47.5%) and water-soluble antibiotics used (30 of 41 respondents; 73.2%) since the VFD regulations were implemented. 58.8% of clients eliminated all uses of antibiotics for growth promotion while another 17.0% of clients reduced use of antibiotics for growth promotion and 24.2% moved to non-medically important growth promotants.

Roskam et al 2019: Average daily gain and mortality generally increased after intervention, whereas feed conversion and antimicrobial use decreased. Economic performance after interventions was generally higher than before the interventions. Sensitivity analyses on price changes confirm the robustness of the findings.

Roulette et al. 2017: Retention of antimicrobial knowledge was positively associated with retention of bacterial knowledge and, among men, retention of bacterial knowledge was associated with greater wealth. Bacterial and AMR knowledge were not, however, associated with self-reported use of the innovations. Among women, self-reported use of the thermometers was associated with having more children and greater retention of knowledge about the health benefits of the innovations. Whereas

70% of women used their innovations correctly, men performed only 18% of the weight-estimation steps correctly. Men's correct use was associated with schooling, such that high illiteracy rates remain an important obstacle to the dissemination and diffusion of weight-estimation materials.

Shryock 2012: Only a few countries have implemented this regulatory risk assessment intervention. National authorities have categorised antimicrobial classes on the basis of perceived importance to human disease treatment within their countries. The effectiveness of regulatory risk assessment for product approval and label directions is difficult to assess. Products have been approved, with specific label indications and directions for use (or restrictions) to guide the veterinarian in clinical practice, and thus provide for animal health and welfare needs but the outcome, in terms of AMR containment, remains unclear. Unforeseen consequences: injectable antimicrobial products are now viewed as preferable to orally administered products, which may limit commercialisation opportunities for the veterinary pharmaceutical industry and deprive veterinarians of new tools to meet animal health and welfare needs. A negative connotation for human health implications associated with the 'critically important' status, which has now been applied to formulary listings, regulatory evaluations and public debate, resulting in bias against the AMU from this group. The net outcome for vet pharmaceutical companies is that it is possible to obtain approvals for new indications within existing antimicrobial classes, but there may be a longer-term shift of research investment into non-antibiotic product opportunities and away from infectious diseases. Implementation of practice guidelines is ongoing in many countries. While these guidelines have been said to increase awareness of the appropriate use of antibiotics, specific measures of compliance or other objective data are difficult to obtain at a national level. One unforeseen outcome has been to identify the need for additional food animal veterinarians, particularly in remote areas. Moreover, as antimicrobial product labels become more restrictive, veterinarians are likely to become more limited in their ability to meet animal health and welfare needs. Implementation by local producers is dependent on many factors, making compliance a matter of strategic priorities on a case-by-case basis. In general, there has always been a desire to minimise disease on the farm because it reduces profitability and compromises animal health and welfare. However, the paradigm has now shifted to employing alternatives to antibiotics to prevent disease and using antimicrobial products only in at-risk or clinically ill animals. One unforeseen consequence for producers has arisen from food companies or retailers that have developed strict corporate antibiotic use (or non-use) policies that now dictate production practices. An unforeseen effect of the legislative approach to AMU restrictions in particular food animal species has been an increase in therapeutic antimicrobial use, due to increased disease, with only an equivocal impact on human AMR foodborne disease.

Speksnijder et al. 2017: 92 objectives and 262 action points. 1-year effect: AMU on intervention farms was significantly reduced but no significant differences in the rate of reduction between the intervention and control groups could be observed. Reduced AMU did not result in negative effects on animal health and production parameters in both groups. Fostering good collaboration among farmer, veterinarian, and feed adviser and focusing on a limited number of objectives have positive effects on the outcomes of the animal health planning program and AMU. Key factors: On intervention farms, a significant positive relationship was found between the percentage of completed action points at farm level and the percentage reduction in AMU. The level of compliance with action points and the quality of collaboration between farmer and advisers were positively associated with the accomplishment of corresponding objectives. The total number of objectives was negatively associated with the level of compliance with action points and tended to be negatively associated with the percentage reduction in AMU at farm level. Good collaboration among farmer, veterinarian, and feed adviser and ownership in animal health planning on dairy farms have a positive influence on the compliance with action plans and achievement of objectives.

Sun et al. 2018: Expected changes: to improve antibiotic use (rational prescribing of antibiotics), to improve resident's knowledge on rational antibiotics use. Expected impact: to increase knowledge; to indirectly limit the emergence and dissemination of antibiotic resistance.

Tangcharoensathien et al. 2017: Expected changes: It is hoped that the stakeholders' involvement in the plan's development will lead to a genuine sense of stakeholder ownership and the plan's long-term efficacy and sustainability, that the trust-based relationship among the steering committee's long serving technocrats who facilitated the plan's development will strengthen and then also support the plan's effective long-term implementation, and to strengthen the monitoring and evaluation of antimicrobial resistance and develop the surveillance of antimicrobial consumption.

Thamlikitkul et al. 2015: Expected impacts: responsible use of antibiotics, and to stop the acquisition and transmission of AMR. The reduction of preventive and collective treatments was not always possible. The reasons given by veterinarians included the willingness to progressively reduce the preventive use of antibiotics in order not to brutally destabilize the sanitary balance of livestock (six farms), the dilapidated state of the buildings and the associated environmental problems (four farms), the failure of previous attempts (four farms), the need for a medical (3 farms) and the lack of alternative options, the persistence of underlying health problems making it impossible to completely eliminate treatments.

van den Borne et al. 2017: Expected impacts: farmers and vets expect to simultaneously improve udder health and reduce AMU, keeping the country's udder health status constant.

van Dijk et al. 2017: credible and practical recommendations. Outcomes: comprehensive learning for all involved. Expected general changes from 60% of the producers: making changes to their AMU as a result of their participation in the policy development process. Expected changes of practice: practices that reduce, and, where possible, eliminate the need for AM therapies; producers work with their veterinarians to assess and address disease risk regularly; staff engaged in using AMU them responsibly or are adequately supervised by staff who are able to do so/ AMU to prevent disease is minimized/ unified data is collected and used to benchmark and compare medicine use within and between farms in order to work towards further reductions in AMU. Real impact of the policy making process: sharing knowledge and awareness raising. Expected impacts: to reduce and rationalise AMU without compromising animal health and welfare, maintaining the same production levels and health of their herds, better understanding of how participatory approaches with farmers can be applied in a UK context and for promoting more responsible use of veterinary medicines in other livestock species.

Wagstrom 2006: Potential impacts: on the ways in which antibiotics are used in US pork production, decrease of some uses of antibiotics in pork production but little, if any, on antibiotic resistance. Success of the program will be dependent on the effectiveness of delivery channels of the program to the pork producers in the US.

Wielinga et al. 2014: Changes of practice: a strong reduction in the use of avoparcin and others AGP, and therapeutic AMU, farmers change their farming management focusing more on biosecurity, vet became advisors. Impacts: subsequent reduction of glycopeptide-resistant bacteria in animals, increase of consumer confidence in Danish meat and more Danish meat are consumed, increase of the acceptance of new measures, Danish became a model for other countries. Economic impact of removing AGP from pork and poultry in Denmark: the net costs associated with productivity losses estimated at 1.04€ per pig produced and no net cost for poultry. The overall estimated impact for the Danish

economy was a reduction of 0.03% (48 million€) but at an early stage and it could be positively impacted in the long term because of continued improvement in productivity. Costs and benefits were too complex to measure but probably off set compensated by other benefits.